

Perception of the Effectiveness of Cassava Off-taking Activities among Young Contract Farmers in Ogun And Oyo States, Nigeria

Ajala A. O., Ogunjimi, S. I., and Ojo K. O.

Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development, Faculty of Agriculture, Federal University Oye-Ekiti
Corresponding author – kennyola048@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study assessed the perception of the effectiveness of cassava off-taking activities among young contract cassava farmers in Ogun and Oyo State, Nigeria. A three-stage sampling procedure was used for the study. The sampled contract cassava farmers were 398 respondents. Data were summarized with percentages, means, and standard deviation while correlation analysis was used to draw inferences. Also, focus group discussion was summarized using content analysis for the qualitative data. The results showed that mean age was 31 ± 13.2 years, mean annual income was $69,535 \pm 122,617$ and mean household was 4.7 ± 2.79 persons. The results showed that provision of infrastructure was ranked first (mean = 1.50) among others. Also, from the result, off-takers hardly keep agreement with their young contract farmers (mean = 3.0) ranked 1st among others. The results revealed that there was low effectiveness of off-taking activities in which provision of fertilizer applicator (mean = 2.64) was ranked 1st among others. A positive and significant relationship was found between effectiveness of off taking activities and age ($r = 0.332$), household size ($r = 0.165$) and farm size ($r = 0.161$). Also, there was positive and significant relationship between perceptions of young contract farmers and their effectiveness of cassava off taking activities ($r = 0.245$). In conclusion, the perception of young contract farmers towards effectiveness of cassava off-taking activities was not positive. It was recommended that an enabling environment should be created by the off-takers and government to boost cassava tuber roots in cassava off-taking activities.

Keywords: Effectiveness; Off-taking; Contract and Perception

INTRODUCTION

Cassava value chain in cassava off-taking industry entails converting fresh roots into High Quality Cassava Flour (HQCF), starch, sweeteners, dried chips, high quality meal (*garri and fufu*), and fuel ethanol which will increase income of farmers and enable them get maximum benefit from crop production (Will, 2020). Off-taking activities entails a forward agreement that specifies obligations of farmers and buyers as partners in business, it stipulates farmers' (sellers') obligations to supply produce according to specified volume and quality, and the buyers' (processors'/traders') obligations to provide production services such as inputs, finance, extension, training, transports and logistics while also off-taking the produce and making payments as agreed upon (Will, 2020). Hence, according to Katharina and Denise (2020), off-taking activities is defined as binding arrangements through which a firm ensures her supply of agricultural produce from an individual or groups of farmers. It facilitates a specially designed trade agreement between producers, processors and traders leading to a vertical integration of the agricultural value chain.

According to Adesina (2019) and Adofu *et al.*, (2021), the array of quality services meant to backstop young farmers right from land preparation to post-harvest management are very vital if young Nigerian farmers will favourably compete with their counterparts elsewhere in the world, hence, the weakness of agri-

support services available to young cassava farmers in Nigeria. Sanni *et al.* (2019) also observed inefficient market information system in Nigerian cassava sub-sector; there is a wide gap from farmers to processors and end-users, and no adequate and prompt information on market trends to appropriately control each of these activities. As young contract farmers (in-grower and out-grower) scheme cassava partner with off-takers, most of their farming constraints, risks and uncertainties become a joint responsibility. Arising from the principle of backward integration and the expectation to off-take young contract farmers (in-grower and out-grower) output, off-takers possess sufficient morale and economic justification to finance young contract farmers (in-grower and out-grower) production and monitor the optimal utilization of production resources advanced for better output (Ewubare and Ologhadien, 2019). This is the platform upon which young contract farmers of forty years or less (in-grower and out-grower) scheme fits into the current status of Nigerian cassava off-taking activities. However, this essentially demands an equitable management of the scheme, as partners in the arrangement could maltreat one another. It is against this backdrop that this study assessed the effectiveness of off-taking activities among young contract cassava farmers in the study area.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. describe the socio-economic characteristics of young contract cassava farmers in the study area,
2. identify the off-taking activities received by the young contract cassava farmers,
3. examine the perception of young contract cassava farmers towards off-taking activities and
4. assess the effectiveness of off-taking activities among young contract cassava farmers.

Hypothesis of the study

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between selected socio-economic characteristics and effectiveness of off taking activities

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between perception of young contract cassava farmers towards off-taking activities and the activities' effectiveness

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Oyo and Ogun States. Agriculture is a predominant occupation in Oyo and Ogun States with about 70% rural population of contract cassava farmers and off-takers companies (Abegunde, 2021). A multi-stage sampling procedure were used for the study. At the first stage, Ogun and Oyo States were purposively selected for the study, because most of the large-scale cassava off-takers (29 agro-industrial companies) in the southwestern zone in Nigeria were located in these states. The second stage was purposive selection of twenty five percent major cassava off-takers in the study area, leading to selection of three and five major cassava off-takers from Ogun and Oyo States respectively; these included Premium Cassava Products Limited, Osoa, Moko Investment, Oke-Odan, Harvest Feeds and Agro-processing Limited, Abeokuta, Ogun State; Psaltry Company International, Ado-Awaye, Eagleson Farm, Iseyin, 365 Farms, Saki, AtmanCorp Nigeria Limited, Ido, and Niji Farm Limited, Oyo State. Then the lists of contracts sampled cluster cassava farmers with each of these off-takers were obtained. Ogun and Oyo States as at the time of this sampling frame has 1030 and 1620 clusters of young contract cassava farmers respectively.

At third stage a simple random sampling of a selection of fifteen percent of the young contract cassava farmers were selected from each of the sampled clusters. The sampled young contract cassava farmers were 155 in Ogun State and 243 in Oyo State giving a total of 398 sampled young contract cassava farmers.

Cassava off-taking activities received by young contract farmers was measured by asking the respondents off-taking activities received from off-takers, yes (1 point) and no (0 point). Frequency and percentage were used to classify the off-taking activities received. Perception was measured by allowing the respondents to react to 20 perceptual statements on a 5-point Likert scale of strongly agree (5 points), agree (4 points), undecided (3 points) disagree (2 points), and strongly disagree (1 point) for positive statements while negative statements were scored in reverse manner. The total obtainable maximum score was 100 and the minimum score of 20. Using mean and standard deviation, the level of perception was classified as favorable or positive, indifferent or undecided, and unfavorable or negative. Effectiveness was measured by allowing the respondents to react to basic cassava off-taking activities on a 5-point Likert scale of not effective (1 point), fairly effective (2 points), rarely effective (3 points), effective (4 points) and highly effective (5 points). The total obtainable maximum score was 150 and the minimum score of 30. Using mean and standard deviation, the level of effectiveness was classified high, medium and low. Focus group discussion was analyzed using thematic content analysis for the qualitative data from the farmers. According to information garnered during pre-survey visits made to some of the major cassava off-takers in the study area, the young contract cassava farmers clusters in the study area were observed to contain between eight and ten young farmers each as supported by IDH-Rockefeller Foundation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of the respondents

The results in Table 1 showed that majority (54.8%) of the young contract cassava farmers were between 21 – 30 years of ages while (45.2%) were between 31 – 40 years. The relative younger ages of the farmers may also enhance their effectiveness in off-taking activities as they may see them as their peers and colleagues. Many (67.6%) of the young contract cassava farmers in the study area were married. The marital status of the cassava farmers has implication on the household size and subsequently on the availability of family labour to assist on the farm. This result is against the report of Ayantoye (2021), who found that 87.1% of the cassava farmers in Oyo State were married. Household size of young contract cassava farmers in the study area has a mean value of 4.7 with standard deviation of 2.79. This implies that household size does not have a direct impact on young contract cassava farming as the findings indicated that the

cassava farmers make use of their household for farming enterprise. This result corresponds with the discoveries of Akinbola *et al.* (2022) who found that young cassava farmers in Akoko district, Ondo state have a mean household size of 5. Result in Table 1 shows that many (60.1%) of the young contract cassava farmers had less than or equal to 3 extension contacts, 31.2% had between 4 and 7 extension contacts, 4.5% had above 8 extensions contact while 4.3% had no extension contacts. The mean extension contact was 3.4 and standard deviation of 2.3. This implies that the majority (60.1%) of the young cassava farmers had low contacts with extension; this implies that the activities of extension agents in the study area are poor. This confirms Kaka *et al.*, (2020) assertion that majority (63%) of the young cassava farmers in Kebbi state had no contact with extension. Result in Table 1 shows that majority (88.2%) of the young contract cassava farmers belong to the Yoruba ethnic group, 8.5% belong to the Hausa ethnic group while

3.3% belong to the Igbo ethnic. This implies that cassava production is not restricted to a particular ethnic group, but it is practiced mostly by Yoruba which is the majority ethnic group in the study area. The mean annual income of young contract cassava farmers in the study area has a mean value of ₦122,617 with standard deviation of ₦69,535. Result in Table 1 shows that majority (95.2%) of the young contract cassava farmers earn less than ₦200,000, while 2.3% earned between ₦201,000 to ₦400,000, 1.3% earned between ₦401,000 – ₦600,000 and 1.3% earned above ₦600,000. This implies that majority (95.2%) of the respondents still have low incomes from their cassava farming and this may be due to the fact that majority of them are small scale farmers. The finding is in line with the study of Mgbakor (2017), his findings revealed that the annual income of cassava producers in Enugu state was low with a mean of ₦171,963.82.

Table 1: Distribution of cassava farmers by their Age, Marital Status, Household Size, extension contact, ethnic group and annual income (n = 398)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD
Age				
21 – 30 years	218	54.8	31	13.2
31 – 40 years	180	45.2		
Marital status				
Single	110	27.6		
Married	269	67.6		
Divorced	12	3.0		
Widowed	7	1.8		
Household Size				
< 5	202	50.8		
5 -10	185	46.5	4.7	2.79
≥ 11	11	2.7		
Extension Contact				
≤3				
4 – 7	239	60.1		
8 and above	124	31.2	3.4	2.3
No contact	18	4.5		
	17	4.3		
Ethnic group				
Yoruba	341	88.2		
Hausa	34	8.5		
Igbo	13	3.3		
Annual income				
≤200,000	379	95.2		
201,000 – 400,000	9	2.3	122,617	69.535
401,000 – 600,000	5	1.3		
>600,000	5	1.3		

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Cassava off-taking activities received by the young contract farmers

Cassava off-taking activities received by the young contract farmers were presented in descending order. The results revealed that majority (89.2%) of respondents received capacity building such as training, workshop and field days, 87.9% said they received cassava stem as cassava off-taking activities, 85.9% received advisory services, 80.4% received fertilizers as off-taking activities and 79.1% received herbicides as off-taking activities among others. The implications of the result are that off-takers had a lot of off-taking activities rendered to young farmers which helps them in their yield size, expansion of farm size among others. The findings on off-taking activities rendered to young contract cassava farmers were consistent with those of Fadairo and Alarape (2020), who found that training on good agricultural practices, provision of fertilizers, provision of pesticide/herbicides and credit support or linkage were among the agri-support services and inputs available to cassava farmers.

This finding was supported by excerpt from the Focus Group Discussion sessions conducted across the study area:

They rendered off-taking activities such as fertilizer, loans, cassava stems. In 2024 cassava contract farming cycle, our group approached the company for loans on weed control management practices for our farm. The company gave us criteria for the loans and after our group met the condition. The loans were released to us in group. We really appreciate our current farm expansion of two hectares each provided to us. (FGD, excerpt from a Young Contract Cassava Farmers from ATMANCorp Nigeria Limited, Ance, Oyo State)

Provision of tractor, training on GAP (Good Agronomical Practices), access to loans has given us a tremendous confidence of participating as a contract cassava farmers with our company. Our relationship has been great with them because of how they ease us with some activities in cassava farming and with a good output on average of 20 tonnes per hectare (FGD, excerpt from a Young Contract Cassava Farmers from Flour Mill Nigeria, Ososa, Ogun State).

Table 2: Off-taking activities received by young contract cassava farmers

Services received	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Offering of capacity building	355	89.2	1st
Provision of cassava stem	350	87.9	2 nd
Provision of advisory services	342	85.9	3rd
Provision of fertilizers	320	80.4	4th
Provision of herbicide	315	79.1	5th
Provision of pesticides	299	75.1	6th
Provision of insecticides	281	70.6	7th
Provision of transport services	277	69.6	8th
Linkages to market	268	67.3	9th
Provision of loan	264	66.3	10th
Allocation of land	258	64.8	11th
Provision of grants	240	60.3	12th
Provision of infrastructure (payment gateway)	199	50.0	13th

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Perception of young contract farmers towards cassava off-taking activities

The table 3 presents the ranked respondents' perceptions of young contract farmers towards cassava off-taking activities in descending order. Apart from off-takers hardly keep agreement with their young contract farmers that has a mean of 3.0, other perception statement have mean value below 3 hence, it means that majority of the respondents had negative

perceptions towards off-taking activities. From the result off-takers hardly keep agreement with their young contract farmers (mean= 3.0) ranked 1st, user-companies under the scheme offer farmers little or no provision of farm inputs (mean = 2.96) ranked 2nd, off-takers often cheat contract cassava farmers under their scheme (mean= 2.85) ranked 3rd, off-takers are never ready to treat farmers as equal business partners (mean= 2.74) ranked 4th, off-takers field staff ready to

treat farmers as equal business partners (mean= 2.72) ranked 5th among others.

The consequence of this perspective is that young contract cassava farmers do not have positive perception about off-taking activities. This is

evidenced by their belief that off-takers often cheat young contract cassava farmers under their scheme. These findings gave credence to Alarape and Akanbi (2021); who reported that more than half of the out growers have positive perception towards the young contract farming scheme.

Table 3: Perception of contract cassava farmers towards off-taking activities

Perceptual statement	Strongly disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Undecided (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly agree (%)	Mean	Rank
Off-takers hardly keep agreement with their contract cassava farmers	45 (11.3)	138 (34.7)	45 (11.3)	113 (28.4)	57 (14.3)	3.00	1st
User-companies under the scheme offer farmers little or no provision of farm inputs	53 (13.3)	114 (28.6)	57 (14.3)	112 (28.1)	62 (15.6)	2.96	2nd
Off-takers often cheat contract cassava farmers under their scheme	40 (10.1)	119 (29.9)	60 (15.1)	101 (25.4)	78 (19.6)	2.85	3rd
Off-takers are never ready to treat farmers as equal business partners	19 (4.8)	134 (33.7)	56 (14.1)	102 (25.6)	87 (21.9)	2.74	4th
Off-takers field staff appear to display partiality in favour of the company	36 (9.0)	100 (25.1)	65 (16.3)	111 (27.9)	86 (21.6)	2.72	5th

Source: Field survey, 2024

Effectiveness of off-taking activities

Data in Table 3 showed that the effectiveness of off-taking activities in descending order. Provision of fertilizer application (mean = 2.64) was ranked 1st, Use of tractor for ridging (mean = 2.62) ranked 2nd, provision of personal protective equipment (mean = 2.55) ranked 3rd, provision of cutlass (mean = 2.51) ranked 4th, use of tractor for harrowing (mean = 2.51) ranked 4th, provision of boom sprayer (mean = 2.48) ranked 6th, provision of sprayer (mean = 2.46) ranked 7th, provision of cassava planter (mean = 2.45) ranked 8th, access to linkage (mean = 2.43) ranked 9th, allocation of farm land to each contract cassava farmer (mean = 2.36) ranked 10th, access to grant (mean = 2.36) ranked 10th, access to loan (mean = 2.31) ranked 12th, availability of in-house farm (mean = 2.29) ranked 13th, availability of third party farm (mean = 2.26) ranked 14th, use of tractor for second ploughing (mean = 2.24) ranked 15th, access to market (mean = 2.23) ranked 16th, access to in-house logistics (mean = 2.20) ranked 17th, access to input dealers (mean = 2.18) ranked 18th, Access to third party logistics (mean = 2.14) ranked 19th, detailed and simple memorandum of understanding (mean = 2.10) ranked 20th, provision of pesticides (mean = 2.10) ranked 20th, fair interest rate (mean = 2.05s) ranked 22nd, access to training (mean = 2.03) ranked 23rd, provision of fungicides (mean = 2.01) ranked 24th, provision of fertilizers (mean = 1.99) ranked 25th, fair price rate of

inputs from input dealers (mean = 1.96) ranked 26th, allocation of land to contract cassava farmers (mean = 1.96) ranked 26th, access to input dealers from off takers (mean = 1.92) ranked 28th, use of tractor for ploughing (mean = 1.90) ranked 29th, provision of stems (mean = 1.89) ranked 30th.

The analyses shows that provision of fertilizer was ranked high with contract cassava farmers due to the fact that it might be the major and most effective services been rendered to farmers. The analyses also shows that provision of tactors for land preparation and input such as cutlass was ranked high. This commendable on the off-takers as the services was a major service in gaining traction and yield of the farmers. This shows that the effectiveness of off-taking activities was low, since the mean scores are less than 3. The results revealed that there was low effectiveness of off-taking activities, the findings agree with Okorie *et al* (2021) and Okuduwor *et al.* (2023) who reported low effectiveness in cassava contract farming due to pricing, delay access to finance and agricultural inputs. The implication of the result is that the contract cassava farmers do not see the off-taking activities as being effective due to the constraints faced by the farmers. The implication of the result is that the contract cassava farmers do not see the off-taking activities as being effective due to the constraints faced by the farmers. If the

constraints faced by the farmers such as inadequate farm land, inadequate labour, untimely supply of inputs, and others are adequately taken care of, it could lead to improved effectiveness of off-taking activities.

The finding was supported by excerpt from the FGD sessions conducted across the study area area
The resources off-takers made available for young contract cassava farmers in off-taking activities such as land allocation, use of tractor, provision of grants,

provision of loans, linkages to market, provision of agro-chemicals as made the programme effective.

The effectiveness of the off-taking activities from off-takers had made a lot of farmers loyal, honest and work in accordance to the organizational structure. This is a big game in cassava revolution in Nigeria which has been a win-win situations to both farmers and off-takers (FGD excerpt from Cassava Contract Farmers from 365 Farm, Saki, Oyo State)

Table 3: Effectiveness of off-taking activities

Variables	Mean	Rank
Provision of fertilizer applicator	2.64	1st
Use of tractor for ridging	2.62	2nd
Provision of personal protective equipment	2.55	3rd
Provision of cutlass	2.51	4th
Use of tractor for harrowing	2.51	4th
Provision of boom sprayer	2.48	6th
Provision of sprayer	2.46	7th
Provision of cassava planter	2.45	8th
Access to linkage	2.43	9th
Allocation of farm land to each contract cassava farmers	2.36	10th
Access to grant	2.36	10th
Access to loan	2.31	12th
Availability of in-house farm	2.29	13th
Availability of third-party farm	2.26	14th
Use of tractor for second ploughing	2.24	15th
Access to market	2.23	16th
Access to in-house LG	2.20	17th
Access to input dealers	2.18	18th
Access to third party LG	2.14	19th
D&S Memorandum	2.10	20th
Provision of pesticides	2.10	20th
Fair interest rate	2.05	22nd
Access to training	2.03	23rd
Provision of fungicides	2.01	24th
Provision of fertilizers	1.99	25th
Fair price rate	1.96	26th
Allocation of land to CCF	1.96	26th
Access to input dealers from off takers	1.92	28th
Use of tractor for ploughing	1.90	29th
Provision of stems	1.89	30th

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between the selected socio-economic characteristics and effectiveness of off taking activities

Table 5 shows the result of correlation analysis of the variables. A positive and significant correlations were found between effectiveness of off taking activities and age ($r = 0.332$), household size ($r = 0.165$) and farm ($r = 0.161$), r^2 (coefficient of determination) in Table 5 shows the percentage variation in Y variable (effectiveness of off taking activities) as explained by each of the X variables in the study. Also, 0.1%

variation in effectiveness of off taking activities was attributed to age, 0.4% variation in effectiveness of off taking activities was attributed to household size, 0.2% variation in effectiveness of off taking activities was attributed to farm size. This result implies that the higher the age, the higher the effectiveness of off taking activities, also, the larger the household size, the higher the effectiveness of off taking activities and the larger the farm size, the higher the effectiveness of off taking activities. Based on the result presented in the table below, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 5: Correlation analysis showing the relationship between some selected socio-economic characteristics of contract cassava farmers and their effectiveness of off taking activities

Variables	Pearson Correlation Coefficient r	Coefficient of determination r^2	Decision	Percentage Contribution %
Age	0.332**	0.110	S	0.1
Household size	0.203**	0.041	S	0.4
Farm size	0.161**	0.026	S	0.2

Source: Field Survey, 2024

** Significant at 0.01 level of significance

Hypothesis two: There is no significant relationship between perception of contract cassava farmers towards off-taking activities and the effectiveness of off taking activities. Result in Table 6 shows the result of correlation analysis of the variables. A positive and significant correlations were found between perception of contract cassava farmers towards off-taking activities and the effectiveness of off taking activities ($r = 0.245$). r^2 (coefficient of determination) in Table 6 shows the percentage variation in Y variable (effectiveness of off taking activities) as explained by

each of the X variables in the study. 0.6% variation in effectiveness of off taking activities was attributed to perception of contract cassava farmers towards off-taking activities. This result implies that the more favourable the perception of contract cassava farmers, the higher the effectiveness of off taking activities. This finding is consistent with Abegunde (2021) who reported that perception of out-growers was significantly related to the effectiveness of cassava out-grower scheme. Based on the result presented in the table below, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 6: Correlation analysis showing the relationship between perception of contract cassava farmers towards off-taking activities and the effectiveness of off taking activities

Variables	Pearson Correlation Coefficient r	Coefficient of determination r^2	Decision	Percentage Contribution %
Perception of farmers	0.245**	0.060	S	0.6

Source: Field Survey, 2024

** Significant at 0.01 level of significance

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study was concluded that contract cassava farmers have unfavourable or negative perception towards effectiveness of cassava off-taking activities in Ogun and Oyo state and there was positive and significant correlation between perception of the young contract cassava farmers and the effectiveness of off-taking activities. The study found that access to ready cassava market and increased income significantly influence

contract cassava farmers' participation in cassava value chain activities. Hence, government should formulate policies that will promote contract cassava farming arrangements as a veritable tool to arrest the cyclical market problem in Nigerian cassava sub-sector and boost farmers' income which invariably will reduce poverty among them. An enabling environment should be created by the off-takers and government and made available for contract cassava

farmers especially agri-supports services to boost cassava tuber roots and enhance positive perception in cassava value chain.

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